

Original Research Article

Assess Knowledge, Attitudes and Practices Regarding Diabetes among Diabetic People in Community, Lahore Pakistan

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Abstract

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The objective of this study was to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of diabetic people regarding diabetes in the community. The design of this study was quantitative descriptive cross sectional to assess knowledge, attitude and practice of diabetic people regarding diabetes in the community. The study was held in the community of Lahore for 6 months. In this analysis, a quantitative descriptive cross-sectional design was used. The diabetic people had a sample size of 150. The purpose of this study is to examine the awareness, attitude and experience of diabetic people about diabetes. SPSS version 21 analyzed the results, mean and standard deviation was used to assess diabetic people' awareness attitude and practices on diabetes. The overall experience of the diabetic people was positive and the attitude of the mean was less than experience and of practice is negative. A conducted study helped to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding diabetes among diabetic people in the community of Lahore. The major aim of the study was that it helped to intend and execute or implement the evidence-based interventions in order to achieve betterment in managing diabetes. The results of the study showed positive knowledge among diabetic people regarding diabetes in the community. They showed some positive attitudes regarding treatment and prevention of diabetes but still there is deficiency in their preventive measures and treatments. Therefore, educational programs or health education must be held in hospitals, health care settings of the community in order to provide a large access of knowledge related to diabetes prevention and treatment.

Keywords: Attitude, Diabetes, Knowledge, Practices

INTRODUCTION

There are several types of diseases in the human natural body. Some diseases affect our daily life functions but have less impact while others become fatal for the human body. Some diseases play a role as silent killers for human life. Diabetes is one of such toxic diseases. Diabetes is defined as a type of human disorder in which

there will be inability to produce natural insulin. Insulin is a type of hormone of the endocrine system. Breakdown of the food particles takes place to make it digestible so it will be converted into energy (sugar or glucose) insulin helps in transportation of the converted energy to the cells of the human body. In actuality, the key role of

insulin is to convey the instructions to body cells to open and receive glucose or energy. In case if there is less ability or no ability of producing insulin or if the human body becomes insulin resistant then sugar or glucose remains in a larger amount inside the cells. The blood glucose level proved to be higher than normal in diabetic patients. There are two types of diabetes in humans i.e., Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes (Abolghasemi et al., 2014).

There are many types of predisposing factors which are becoming the causes of diabetes. These include some Genetics factors i.e., diabetes is a hereditary disorder passing from one generation to another, lifestyle is also a biggest cause of diabetes because sedentary lifestyles contribute to diabetes and environment factors like stress and anxiety can also be causes of diabetes. Moreover, dietary intake is also a major predisposing factor like eating unhealthy diet, having overweight or obese physical body structure, lack of exercise also plays a key role in development of diabetes, especially Type 2 diabetes or diabetes mellitus. While the diabetes mellitus or Type 1 diabetes is mainly caused by an autoimmune response and is known as autoimmune compromised disorder. In Type 1 diabetes the body's immune system directly attacks and destroys specifically the insulin producing beta cells of the pancreas. These cells are also called as Islets of Langerhans of pancreas (Abdoli et al., 2012).

Not only Diabetes itself dangerous but it also plays a silent killer role for the human body. As passing time duration excessive glucose inside the blood of the human body will surely cause serious health complications and hazards. Diabetes can cause damage to eyes or retinopathy, can damage kidneys and may result in renal failure; moreover, Diabetes can cause nerve damage or sensitivity. Cardiac disorders like Cardiomyopathy, cardiovascular diseases, stroke, myocardial infarction. Some severe situations result in removal of limbs. During pregnancy there are changes of diabetes called gestational diabetes but it must be resolved or relieved after pregnancy in case of continuation of gestational diabetes after pregnancy there are risks of severe complications of diabetes even death (Adequate et al., 2013).

Diabetes is becoming a major and hazardous health disorder. Universally it is affecting more than 171 million people and there are high expectations that this figure will rise to 366 million by 2030. 90 per cent of all reported cases are due to Type 2 Diabetes. As a developing country Pakistan is having 9.5% of the population in urban and 9.4% of the rural population which are suffering from type 2 diabetes. In accordance with the WHO estimation, Pakistan is ranked seventh in prevalence of Diabetes. Still such facts and figures only represent the tip of the iceberg with several cases which are undiagnosed. Nevertheless, of all the applied and conducted researches diabetes still remained under diagnosed. And then such under diagnosed diabetes

enlightens up with severe complications. They are enormous in direct and indirect costs. The main aim of diabetes healthcare is improvement of quality of life of diabetic patients mainly through glycemic control, control of predisposing factors, modification of lifestyles and health education on preventing diabetes and its complications (World health organization, 2012).

Health education on diabetes is becoming the basis towards healthcare of diabetes. Betterment in training of basic healthcare providers and the diabetic patients hence its very helpful. Different types of research of family doctors highlighted the need of improving the practices in treating diabetes and educating techniques regarding diabetes betterment. In Pakistan, the people are less educated and hence there is lack of information regarding knowledge and attitudes pertaining to controlling glycemic, complications of diabetes and the health effects of diabetes. In addition, there are few studies conducted in Karachi Pakistan but the data collected was not so dense to have a better conclusion. Through Health education related to diabetes the awareness of diabetic people about their facing disorder will be enhanced, misconceptions regarding diabetes especially about dietary pattern and insulin hormone and its functions, will also be cleared after conducting effective research. Most importantly the community regions deserve more intense considerations about diabetes. People with lower educational status must receive proper teaching on the prevention of diabetes (Ambiguity et al., 2003).

Purpose of the study

The purpose of my study is to assess knowledge, attitude and practice of diabetic people regarding diabetes in the community.

Objective

To assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of diabetic people regarding diabetes in the community.

Research Questions

What is the knowledge attitude and practices of diabetic people regarding diabetes in the community?

Significance of the study

This study helped researchers to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding diabetes among diabetic people in the community of Lahore. The majority of people as the residents of communities (rural areas)

are unaware of diabetes, predisposing factors and serious complications related to diabetes. More access and information on this topic have intensely minimized or diminished the adverse outcomes related to diabetes. Moreover, wide informational aspects have enhanced the suffering of diabetic people.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to this study, several studies are conducted within the past exploring the KAP towards DM. A recent study conducted among the diabetic patients of Western Asian nations reportable poor KAP scores one additionally the plausible factors may be lack of awareness, inconvenience of data and acquisition level of the study population. Another recent study involving young (31-40 years) diabetic Saudi ladies also reported poor KAP scores eight. The authors of the previous reports finished that implementation of adequate awareness programs might enhance the KAP that successively would improve the management of DM.

In Malaysia, Ranjini et al. reported that diabetic patients in an exceedingly medical aid center had smart data and higher perspective towards the care of their own malady. It absolutely was not reported whether or not the knowledge and attitude translated into practices as counseled by the management guidelines. They additionally failed to leave the particular management of DM in their study population. Another study by Wong et al reported vital suboptimal care of polygenic disease in Malaysian primary care centers wherever 38% of diabetics achieved good glycaemic control. However, the authors of the study did not inquire into the KAP towards DM in their study participants.

A cross-sectional study has been done to judge data, perspective and applications concerning polygenic disorder among Iranian sort a pair of diabetic patients in Ahvaz, Iran. Overall, it had been found that diabetic patients had depleted knowledge regarding the symptoms, complications, bar and management of their disease condition. The KAP score for the bulk of the patients was on medium level. However, a study from Malaya rumored an honest knowledge, attitude and practice score among diabetic patients. The variations within the results of studies could also be because of the differences in academic level of the diabetic patients and accessibility of data and diabetes education.

A hospital primarily based cross sectional study was undertaken to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices of 730 sort a pair of diabetic patients attending the diabetic clinic at B.M. Patil medical school and hospital. The mean age of the respondents was appreciating the mean age of $53.3 \pm$ thirteen years found in a very similar study. Surveys indicate that prevalence rises steeply with age. sort 2 DM typically involves lightweight within the middle years of life and thenceforth

begins to rise in frequency. It is encouraging to notice that the majority of the respondents in our study had truthful or good data concerning malady} and regarded diabetes to be a significant condition, with diet enjoying a very important role up to speed of diabetes and were inclined to be told additional regarding the disease. Findings disclosed that with increasing periods of diabetes, knowledge additionally increases. This might be as a result of longer duration, there are more occasions for exposure to information regarding diabetes. Similar association between knowledge and longer disease duration has also been rumored among diabetic respondents.

In Saadia et al.'s study in Asian nations patients had identical data because the present study whereas their angle and apply were lower. Saadia et al. assessed feminine diabetic patients. Age and sort of treatment were related to knowledge, attitude, and practice in Tan and Magarey's study in Asian nations that is in accordance with the current study.

In Nepal, Upadhyay's study showed less data and follow and similar angle compared to gift study, with this distinction that they evaluated newly-diagnosed patients. However, Singh et al. assessed patients in 2 groups: governmental and non-governmental hospitals of Nepal. Patients in non-governmental hospitals had a similar knowledge because the patients within the present study, whereas those in governmental hospitals had less knowledge. They didn't assess patients' attitude and practice.

An institutional based mostly cross-sectional study was conducted in the region of Nepal by Anju Gautam, Dharma Nand Bhatta by employing a non-probability sampling technique to pick the diabetic patients. a complete of 244 diabetic patients were interviewed from Gregorian calendar month to November 2014. Knowledge was collected by face-to-face interview victimization structured questionnaire rater questionnaires. Relative risk quantitative relation (RRR) and 95 % confidence interval (CI) of associated factors were calculable by a stepwise probability ratio methodology with multinomial logistic regression. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted in Cheranalloor Panchayat (self-administration unit) of Ernakulum District, Kerala, India. Six wards were randomly chosen from the 16 wards of the panchayat. From the selected wards, 190 houses were randomly visited. Adults aged 20 years and above, who were willing and available at the time of visit were interviewed. A total of 343 individuals were interviewed. For any house with more than one eligible person, interview was carried out separately to avoid any family influence. In addition to baseline data on sociodemographic characteristics and family history of diabetes mellitus, the questionnaire covered different aspects of diabetes mellitus. Besides, enquiry about diabetes status (self-reported) was made. Socioeconomic status was assessed by Prasad's Social Scale. There

were a total of 23 questions, four on the general awareness of diabetes mellitus, six on the risk factors, six on the treatment and complications, and five on the lifestyle modifications. All 23 questions were scored. The possible response for closed question

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Design

A descriptive cross sectional study is designed to figure out assessing the knowledge attitude and practice of diabetic people regarding diabetes.

Sample Size

The population of this study was selecting the diabetic people of the community. The target population consists of 150 participants and all was diabetic people of community.

Study Setting: This study was conducted in the Lahore community of Lahore.

Study Population: The diabetic people were selected for the study population

Sampling: Simple Random sampling was used in this study

Research Instrument

A well written structured and adopted questionnaire from the study was used for collecting the data from the participant. After taking informed consent, data was collected from diabetic people of the community.

Data Gathering Procedure

A formal written letter of permission to conduct the research. Also, an ethical approval was obtained from the author to use this questionnaire and the questionnaire was distributed to diabetic people of the community.

Sample Size

Slovin's sampling will be used to find the sample size of the study population.
If the total population is 240

If N=population

n= sample size

E= margin of error

$n = N / 1 + (N) (E)^2$

$n = 240 / 1 + (240) (0.05)^2$

$n = 240 / 1 + (240) (0.0025)$

$n = 240 / 1 + 0.6$

$n = 240 / 1.6$

$n = 150$

Inclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria included all diabetic people especially who were willing to participate in this study and gave informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

Exclusion criteria included who were not willing to participate in this study. This segment also excluded absentees at the time of the data collection process.

Data Collection Techniques

Assess various families of the community for the purpose of identifying problems related to diabetes. Assessment including questionnaire, observations, focus groups, interviews.

Ethical Consideration

In this research ethical consideration was highly preferred. For this purpose, the permission was obtained from the ethical committee of the health care institution, before data collection. Permission was acquired by a written approval from the head of the department of Lahore school of nursing in the form of consent. Furthermore, informed written and verbal consent was taken before data collection from participants. Students were given the right of autonomy and nature. The purpose of the study was informed prior to the implementation of any action. The risk related to this study was discussed before. Participants were given the right to leave the study participation at any time. In this case other participants were added for the accomplishment of data information. Participants were informed about the aims of the study and secrecy of the collected data was assured. A written consent was taken from respondents who were willing to participate in this study. All respondents were informed that their participation is highly appreciated and they can participate voluntarily. Participants were taken in confidence that all the collected information and records remained confidential.

Table 1. Demographic Data

Age of the participants

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
20 to 39 years	53	35.3	35.3	35.3
40 to 59 years	65	43.3	43.3	78.7
60 to 79 years	24	16	16	94.7
Above 80 years	8	5.3	5.3	100
Total	150	100	100	

Table 2. Gender of Participants

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	61	40.7	40.7	40.7
Female	89	59.3	59.3	100
Total	150	100	100	

RESULT AND DATA ANALYSIS

Results and data analysis were taken up through systematic and logical techniques (SPSS) after the accomplishment of the data collection process.

RESULTS

This section presents the outcomes of the study

Profile of the Respondents

Demographic data

Respondents were taken from the Lahore community. The above table 1 shows that ages of diabetic patients were 40 to 59 years (43.3%), 20 to 39 years (35.3%), 60 to 79 years (16%) and above 80 years (5.3%).

The above table 2 shows the gender of diabetic patients was female (59.3%) and male (40.7%).

Table 3. Educational Status of Participants

Education status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Illiterate	15	10	10	10
Primary Education	83	55.3	55.3	65.3
Middle Education	18	12	12	77.3
Higher Education	34	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Table 4. Occupation of Participants

Occupation	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Government Employee	32	21.3	21.3	21.3
Private employee	69	46	46	67.3
Self-Worker	19	12.7	12.7	80
Unemployed	30	20	20	100.0
Total	150	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows the educational status of diabetic patients' primary education (55.3%), higher education (22.7%), middle education (12%) and illiterate (10%).

Table 4 above shows that occupation of diabetic patients was private employee (46%), Government employee (21.3%), Unemployed (20%) and self-worker (12.7%).

RESULTS

Data of research was collected from a total of 150 diabetic patients in community majority n=65 of them

were 40 to 50 years (43.3%). Majority n=89 gender of respondents was female (59.3%). Majority n=83 educational status of diabetic patients was primary education (55.3%). Majority n=69 occupation of them was private employee (46%). Majority n=109 of them were using insulin (72.7%). Majority n=115 of them were taking antihypertensive drugs (76.7%). Majority n=92 of them were taking anticoagulant drugs (61.3%). Majority n=95 of them were taking cholesterol lowering medicines (63.3%). Majority n=102 of them had hypertension (68%). Majority n=126 of them didn't have renal disorder (84%). Majority n=131 of them didn't have retinopathy (87.3%). Majority n=127 of them didn't have neuropathy (84.7%).

Table 5. Section II Knowledge of the diabetic people about diabetes

S.No	Knowledge of the diabetic people	%
1	Do you have knowledge about diabetes?	90.7%
2	Do you know that diabetes decreases insulin in the body?	85.3%
3	Can we control diabetes through diet?	90.7%
4	Can we control diabetes through exercise?	92.7%
5	Is diabetes an inherited disease?	55%
6	Does blood pressure affect sugar level?	90%
7	Does diabetes cause renal disorders?	90%
8	Does diabetes cause retinopathy?	72%
9	Does diabetes cause neuropathy?	69.3%
10	Do you know about neuropathy?	91.3%

Table 6. Attitude of diabetic people about Diabetes

Sr.No	Attitudes of the diabetic people	%
1	Diabetes is a treatable disorder?	94%
2	Is diabetes treated through diet and exercise?	84.7%
3	Does Diabetes decrease life expectancy?	77.3%
4	Herbal medications are less complex than physician's medicines?	91.3%
5	Do diabetic patients should control their sugar level?	92%
6	Can regular exercise control sugar level?	56.7%
7	Does initiation of insulin can become more complex?	56%
8	Does treated diabetes can decrease risk of blindness and kidney disorders?	54.7%
9	Does smoking increase complications of diabetes?	59.3%
10	Does lipid increase the complications of diabetes?	51.3%

Table 7. Practices of the diabetic people about diabetes

Sr.No	Practices of diabetic people	%
1	Do you visit an ophthalmologist?	58%
2	Do you use herbal medications for diabetes?	68%
3	Do you visit a nutritionist?	54.7%
4	Do you take good care of your feet?	78.7%
5	Do you have glucometer?	52.7%
6	Do you exercise daily?	63.3%
7	Do you check Blood sugar Level daily?	90.7%

Majority n=136 of them had knowledge regarding diabetes (90.7%). Majority n=128 of them knew that diabetes decreases insulin in the human body (85.3%). Majority n=136 of them agreed to the statement that diabetes can be controlled through diet (90.7%). Majority n=136 of them agreed that diabetes is a genetic disorder (90.7%). Majority n=131 of them agreed to the statement that blood pressure affects blood sugar level (87.3%). Majority n=135 of them agreed that diabetes can cause renal diseases (90%). Majority n=135 of diabetic people agreed that diabetes can cause retinopathy (90%). Majority n=108 of them didn't know how to control their sugar level (72%). Majority n=104 of them didn't know about neuropathy (69.3%). Majority n=137 of them agreed to the statement that diabetes is a treatable disease (91.3%). Majority n=141 agreed to the statement that diabetes is treated through diet and exercise (94%).

Majority n=127 agreed that diabetes decreases life expectancy (84.7%). Majority n=116 agreed to it that herbal medications are less complex than physician's medicines (77.3%). Majority n=137 agreed to this statement that diabetic patients should control their cholesterol and blood pressure (91.3%). Majority n=138 of them agreed that regular exercise can control diabetes (92%). Majority n=85 of diabetic people disagreed that smoking increases the effects of diabetes (56.7%). Majority n=84 of them disagreed that cholesterol increases the effects of diabetes (56%). Majority n=89 of them visit an ophthalmologist (54.7%). Majority n=89 of diabetic people didn't use herbal medications for treating diabetes (59.3%). Majority n=77 of them didn't visit a nutritionist for treating diabetes (51.3%). Majority n=87 of diabetic people took good care of their feet (58%). Majority n = 102 of them do not exercise daily (68%).

Majority n=82 of diabetic people had their personal glucometer (54.7%). Majority n=118 didn't check their blood sugar level (BSR) routine wise (78.7%). Majority n=79 of them did not take regular meals thrice a day (52.7%). Majority n=95 of them didn't visit a physician for treating diabetes (63.3%). Majority n=136 of them didn't smoke or consume alcohol (90.7%).

DISCUSSION

Current study was conducted on the knowledge, attitude and practices of diabetic people in the community of Lahore, Pakistan. A previous study was conducted in Iranian Diabetic people. In this past study, a higher general knowledge score in data analysis was shown. In present study, the diabetic people were mostly middle aged. Majority of them were females with primary education and private employment as their occupation. Many researches on Iranian diabetic patients' interpreting the KAP level are published in native language in other cities of Iran. This current study was conducted in the community of Lahore Pakistan to interpret the results and findings. The diabetic people were in decent level after some successful experiences carried out for cultivating the Knowledge Attitude and Practice level in Lahore, Pakistan. In this present study overall KAP score of diabetic people in the community was enhanced much more than the previous relative studies. Many educational programs have been held in the past. But this level of KAP is not optimal currently and this KAP could be better by continuing these provided education programs. The present study is in concordance with Niroomand et al. in that both examined the relationship between age and disease duration with patients' knowledge and practice; with the difference that they did not evaluate patients' attitude and that gender was correlated with practice in their study where male participants showed better practice. All patients in Niroomand et al.'s study showed lower knowledge and practice in Iran. While in the present study mostly females showed participation in the survey. In Nepal, Upadhyay's study showed less knowledge and practice and similar attitude in comparison to present study, with this difference that they evaluated newly-diagnosed patients among the community of Lahore, Pakistan. But Singh et al. assessed patients in two groups: governmental and non-governmental hospitals of Nepal. Patients in non-governmental hospitals had the same knowledge as the patients in the present study, while those in governmental hospitals had less knowledge. They did not assess patients' attitude and practice. Similar to the present study, low knowledge of diabetic patients about optimal blood pressure and importance of its control was pointed out in a study in Australia done by Wong et al. In Saadia et al.'s study in Saudi Arabia patients had the same knowledge as the present study

while their attitude and practice were lower as compared to present study. Saadia et al. assessed female diabetic patients similarly the present study also included mostly females. Age and type of treatment were associated with knowledge, attitude, and practice in Tan and Magarey's study in Malaysia which is in accordance with the present study. Age was negatively correlated with practice; younger people pay less attention towards their health issues, while the knowledge and attitude were at an improved level in old aged diabetic people. Therefore, concentrating on practice of older people could be measured in future educational plans. In the present study diabetic people were using insulin, taking antihypertensive, anticoagulants, cholesterol lowering drugs for treating diabetes similar to the previous study. In this current study diabetic people had hypertension similar to past study. Whereas, this present study involves no occurrence of renal disorders, retinopathy, neuropathy in diabetic people while in past study. such disorders were highly occurring. In current study diabetic people agreed that diabetes is treatable disease in accordance with past study. Moreover, in the present study diabetic people agreed diet and exercise can control diabetes with study conducted in the past. Similar to past study. A present study showed that diabetes decreases life expectancy. In accordance with past study this present study showed that herbal medicines are less complex than physician's medications. Additionally, current study showed that diabetic people showed control of their cholesterol and blood pressure similar to past study. Diabetic people highly agreed that regular exercise decreases risk and effects of diabetes similar to past study. Current study showed that initiative use of insulin increases complexity similar to past study. Moreover, present study analyzed that smoking increases effects of diabetes similar to past study. In India, Rathod et al. described the general population of India and showed lower KAP level, but Raj and Angadi showed higher KAP level in comparison to the present study. In Raj and Angadi's study, longer disease duration was significantly associated with higher knowledge which is in agreement with the findings of the present study. Demaio et al., evaluating KAP in the general population in Mongolia, reported that one fifth of them had no knowledge about diabetes and had a high rate of incorrect conceptions about diabetes and its symptoms. One third of the study population was not aware of diabetes preventability by changing lifestyle in their study. In the present study, surveys with high validity and reliability were useful under the supervision of expertise, and knowledge, attitude and practice were instantaneously evaluated in diabetic people it pointed as the asset of the present study.

Limitation

Study was conducted during a short period of time. Data

was collected from only community by assessing Knowledge, Attitude and Practice among diabetic people only.

CONCLUSION

A conducted study helped to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices regarding diabetes among diabetic people in the community of Lahore. The major aim of the study was that it helped to intend and execute or implement the evidence-based interventions in order to achieve betterment in managing diabetes. The results of the study showed positive knowledge among diabetic people regarding diabetes in the community. They showed some positive attitudes regarding treatment and prevention of diabetes but still there is deficiency in their preventive measures and treatments. Therefore, educational programs or health education must be held in hospitals, health care settings of the community in order to provide a large access of knowledge related to diabetes prevention and treatment.

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